

Project Number: 21-ESOF-019

Application Type

Conference Session

Number of speakers and Moderator

5

Session format

Please provide information on the session format (panel discussion/interactive round table/(hybrid) workshop/House of Commons style...) - 100 words maximum

The session will be a panel discussion. Each of the speakers will be given a limited time to introduce themselves and their main talking points. The session will take the form of a moderated discussion that will give a lot of space for audience participation and the perspectives of each speaker.

Theme

Please specify the conference theme the session/presentation fits into.

Off the beaten track: new paths for Academic Careers

Conference Session/Poster Presentation Title

Creating Research Environments that foster Mental Health and Wellbeing

Top 5 keywords

Five keywords maximum, separated by semicolon; and space

Researcher mental health; Research Culture; Researcher Well-Being; Evidence-based policy making; Academic precarity;

Abstract

450 words maximum

Increasing awareness of Researcher Mental Health has emerged through journalistic articles in the most prominent science journals, in discussions among early-career researchers on social media and bottom-up initiatives of early-career researchers. Recent research findings on the prevalence of mental illness among academics and early career researchers, such as, the seminal paper of Levecque et al. (Research Policy, 2017), have received much attention.

Although much work remains to be done to destigmatise mental health among research stakeholders, many research institutions and research funders are beginning to take action to design institutional practices that support researcher well-being and ensure a positive research culture within the research environment. This session will include speakers, who have formulated clear policy recommendations about how to foster supportive and inclusive research environments.

The Researcher Mental Health and Well-Being Manifesto (Kismihok et al., 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/5559806>) is a call to identify which practices and actions are effective at creating research environments that foster mental health and well-being, reduce mental health stigma, and empower researchers when it comes to well-being in their workplace. The ReMO COST Action provides a framework for involving a network of researchers, practitioners and institutional stakeholders in achieving the objectives of the Manifesto through designing actions and initiatives at the policy, institutional, community and individual levels.

The Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers was updated in 2019 and commits research institutions in the UK to obligations with regard to research environment and culture, employment, and professional and career development. In the updated Concordat, mental health became a key theme of how institutions, funders, supervisors and researchers can promote a healthy research environment.

The career outlook and working conditions of PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers have been addressed by the Marie Curie Alumni Association and Eurodoc in the Declaration on Sustainable Researcher Careers (Kismihok et al., 2019, <https://zenodo.org/record/3082245>) with recommendations to redesign the education of early-career researchers, so that they are empowered to build a more vibrant European Research Area, whether they make a career inside or outside academia. The dysfunctional nature of career progression at the postdoctoral level has been addressed by the OECD report on "Reducing the precarity of academic research careers" (2021, <https://doi.org/10.1787/23074957>) with recommendations "to improve working conditions and professional development, better link funding to human resource policies, make governance

more inclusive, promote equal opportunities and diversity, improve human resource management, promote inter-sectoral and international mobility, and develop the evidence base on research careers”.

Finally, the session will include the perspective of a practitioner from a Counselling Service within an academic institution, who provides psychological, psychotherapeutic and psychiatric services to academic staff and students based on evidence-based interventions.

Speakers

Speaker #1

Title: Dr

First Name: Janet

Last Name: Metcalfe

Gender: Female

Email: janetmetcalfe@btinternet.com

Reason Dr Janet Metcalfe is the Head of Vitae, committed to providing world-class career and professional development for researchers. She is **inviting:** responsible for the strategic direction of Vitae and leads on the 50 words implementation of the UK Concordat to Support the Career maximumDevelopment of Researchers.

Affiliation: Vitae

Country: United Kingdom

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/janet-metcalfe-05b36734/>

Role: Speaker

Status: Confirmed

Speaker #2

Title: Dr

First Name: Neda

Last Name: Bebiroglu

Gender: Female

Email: neda.bebiroglu@frs-fnrs.be

Reason Dr. Neda Bebiroglu is scientific advisor and coordinator at the **for** Observatory of Research and Scientific Careers-F.R.S.-FNRS. She **inviting:** was a member of the OECD Expert Group that produced the report on 50 words "Reducing the precarity of research careers" and hosted the final maximumworkshop.

Affiliation: Observatory of Research and Scientific Careers-F.R.S.-FNRS

Country: Belgium

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/neda-bebiroglu-639102177>

Role: Speaker

Status: Confirmed

Speaker #3

Title: Dr

First Name: Gábor

Last Name: Kismihók

Affiliation: TIB Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology

Country: Germany

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/kismihok/>

Name:

Gender: Male

Role: Speaker

Email: gabor.kismihok@tib.eu

Status: Confirmed

Reason for inviting: Dr. Kismihok leads the Learning and Skills Analytics Group at the

TIB, is Chair of the ReMO COST Action and Chair of the Career

Development Working Group of the MCAA. He is the lead author of

50 words the Researcher Mental Health and Well-Being Manifesto and the

maximumDeclaration on Sustainable Researcher Careers.

Speaker #4

Title: Dr

Affiliation:University of Malta

First

Joan

Country: Malta

Name:

Last

Camilleri

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/dr-joan-camilleri-63488927/>

Name:

Role: Speaker

Gender: Female

Status: Confirmed

Email: joan.camilleri@um.edu.mt

Reason for inviting: Dr. Joan Camilleri is Head of Counselling Services at the University of

Malta where she manages a multi-disciplinary team that provides

50 words psychological, psychotherapeutic and psychiatric services for students

maximum and staff based on evidence-based interventions. She also lectures legal

trainees in mental health and counselling trainees in psychopathology and

gestalt psychotherapy.

Speaker #5

Title: Dr

Affiliation:EuroScience

First

Brian

Country: Germany

Name:

Last

Cahill

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/brian-cahill-0b2123102/>

Name:

Role: Moderator

Gender: Male

Status: Confirmed

Email: brian.cahill@euroscience.org

Reason for inviting: Dr. Brian Cahill is a researcher at the TIB in Hannover Germany and is

Grant Manager of the COST Action on Researcher Mental Health. He

50 words is a Member of the Governing Board of EuroScience and former Chair

maximum of the Marie Curie Alumni Association.